

THE IMPACT OF GKKV ON BIOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN LIVER MITOCHONDRIA INDUCED BY IONIZING RADIATION

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Abstract: Based on information about the role of genetic, structural, and functional disorders of mitochondria in the development of various diseases, a new concept of "mitochondrial diseases" was formed in the late 20th century. When ionizing radiation affects an organism, the peroxidation of lipids is activated, leading to an increase in free radicals and subsequent genetic, structural, and functional changes in mitochondria. These changes may contribute to the development of "mitochondrial diseases." Currently, scientists believe that mitochondrial dysfunctions may cause the development of age-related diseases such as Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, and others. According to researchers, these age-related disturbances in cells are largely attributed to free radicals produced in mitochondria—active forms of oxygen—participating in many biochemical processes.

The activation of oxidative processes involving free radical lipids has been demonstrated by numerous researchers over recent years to contribute to aging and exacerbate pathological conditions within an organism. The activation of lipid peroxidation (LPO) leads to destructive changes within cells. Oxidative stress results in protein denaturation, reduced enzyme activity, damage to the cellular genome, and subsequent progression of pathological processes within the organism. Research findings indicate that when organisms are exposed to ionizing radiation (LPO) processes become active and lead to an increase in free radicals within the body. These radicals begin to exert harmful effects on organic molecules. Damage to DNA can result in various molecular diseases manifesting within the organism. The detrimental effects of free radicals can be counteracted through antioxidant substances.

Currently, understanding how lipid oxidation is related to aging and developing effective methods for correcting defects occurring during this process is a pressing issue that requires searching for antioxidant compounds necessary for restoring important biochemical indicators and providing protection. In recent years, polyphenolic compounds derived from plants have been extensively studied as such substances.

Materials and Methods of the Research: The experiments were conducted using 3, 6, 12, and 15-month-old male laboratory rats that were kept under standard vivarium conditions. A supramolecular complex consisting of glycerin acid and quartz was used as a stabilizing agent. The rats were divided into the following groups: Group 1 control - 3-month-old; Group 2 - "mature" 6-month-old; Group 3 - "mature" rats that received the stabilizing agent; Group 4 - "aged" 12-month-old rats; Group 5 - "aged" rats that received the stabilizing agent; Group 6 - "old" 15-month-old rats; Group 7 - "old" rats that received the stabilizing agent; Group 8 - gamma-irradiated "rapid aging" model rats (irradiation dose of 2 Gr); and Group 9 -

gamma-irradiated "rapid aging" model rats that received the stabilizing agent. The stabilizing agents were administered to the different aged rats for 7 days, while the irradiated rats received it for 15 days at a dosage of GKKV -35 mg per kg body weight. Mitochondria were isolated from the liver of the animals using differential centrifugation.

Results: The activation of free radical lipid oxidation processes is associated with aging and exacerbates pathological conditions in many species of humans and animals. Therefore, using plant preparations containing polyphenols can aid in restoring disrupted homeostasis, preserving cell membrane integrity and structure, reducing lipid peroxidation (LPO) processes, and enhancing antioxidant defense as one of the pathways in the pathogenesis of various diseases that develop with age.

The following table presents changes in MDA levels (a product of LPO processes) in liver cell mitochondria from rats of different ages (n=8; M±m).

№	Experimental variations	MDA n mol/mg protein amount	
		NADFN group	Ascorbate group
1	Control, young (3 months)	0.341±0.013 100%	0.302±0.009 100%
2	Mature (6 months)	0.417±0.027 122%	0.401±0.025 133%
3	Aged (12 months)	0.489±0.018 143%	0.435±0.031 144%
4	Elderly (15 months)	0.575±0.013 169%	0.483±0.026 160%

The table shows that as the age of experimental animals increases, the level of MDA also rises. In "mature" rats, a higher level of MDA was identified compared to 3-month-old rats. In the "aged" rat group, this indicator was 30% higher than that of the 3-month-old rats, while in the "old" rat group, this indicator reached 150%, meaning it was 1.5 times higher than that of younger animals.

To normalize the increased level of MDA, a plant-based polyphenol compound known as GKKV preparation was administered to groups of rats of various ages.

The following table shows the effect of the GKKV plant preparation on the level of MDA in liver mitochondria of rats of different ages (n=8; M±m).

№	Experimental variants	MDA n mol/mg protein amount	
		NADFN group	Ascorbate group
1	Control, young (3 months)	0.341±0.013 100%	0.302±0.009 100%
2	Mature (6 months)	0.417±0.027 122%	0.401±0.025 133%
3	Mature +GKKV (7 months)	0.375±0.013 110%	0.325±0.026 108%
4	Aged(12 months)	0.489±0.018 143%	0.435±0.031 144%
5	Aged +GKKV (7 months)	0.372±0.016 109%	0.383±0.032 127%
6	Elderly (15 months)	0.575±0.013 169%	0.483±0.026 160%
7	Elderly +GKKV (7 months)	0.478±0.021 140%	0.386±0.016 128%

The table shows that GKKV significantly affects the decrease in the amount of MDA, a product of LPO, when administered over a period of 7 days. From the above results, it can be concluded that GKKV influences the lipid components of the mitochondrial membrane and ensures the restoration of the lipid bilayer. GKKV has a high reactivity and exerts a stabilizing effect on the mitochondria membranes of hepatocytes.

Several studies have shown that a dose of 2 Gr of X-ray radiation leads to significant changes in the chromatin structure and protein synthesis in liver cells. The direction of these changes resembles those occurring in aging organisms.

It should be noted that under the influence of the mentioned radiation dose, spontaneous changes characteristic of aging are also observed in other indicators within cells, particularly in the distribution of intracellular electrolytes during LPO processes, microsomal oxidation, and others. For this reason, this model may be useful for studying the effectiveness of hepatoprotective compounds under conditions of accelerated aging. Keeping this in mind, when measuring MDA levels in liver mitochondria from “accelerated aging” model rats, the following results were obtained.

№	Experimental variants	MDA n mol/mg protein amount	
		NADFN group	Ascorbate group
1	Control 6 months	0.312±0.019 100%	0.337±0.014 100%
2	Irradiated 6 months	0.557±0.021 192%	0.512±0.017 189%
3	Irradiated +GKKV(15days)	0.301±0.027 96%	0.313±0.023 93%

The table shows that the amount of the lipid peroxidation (LPO) product MDA in the liver mitochondria of irradiated animals has nearly doubled compared to that in the mitochondria of control rats. However, in irradiated rats that were administered 2 grams of Ginkgo biloba extract (GKKV), it was found that after 15 days of GKKV treatment, the MDA levels significantly decreased.

Conclusion: Therefore, as a result of irradiation at a dose of 2 Gr, LPO is activated in the liver mitochondria of rats, leading to an increase in the level of its product—MDA. This reduces the rate of electron transport in the respiratory chain and disrupts mitochondrial energy production function. ATP synthesis decreases, and all biochemically energy-requiring processes slow down. During this time, administering antioxidants helps reduce LPO processes and aids in prolonging organism lifespan. As rats age, LPO processes become more active, and MDA levels increase; this increase is further exacerbated by irradiation. The plant preparation GKKV significantly reduces MDA levels. GKKV affects lipid components and ensures the restoration of lipid membranes. It helps restore disrupted homeostasis, reduces LPO processes, and we can observe an enhancement in the organism's antioxidant defense.

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